
Informal Sector and Community Development in Oyo Town, Oyo State, Nigeria

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15874748>

Abstract

The informal sector plays a crucial role in community development by providing employment, fostering entrepreneurship and contributing to economic resilience. This study examined the influence of the informal sector on community development in Oyo Town, Oyo State. By assessing the contributions of informal businesses to local economic activities and social cohesion, the research revealed the sector's significant role in combating unemployment and fostering entrepreneurship among youth and adults. Using a mixed-methods approach, data were collected from 150 informal sector operators across four local government areas through structured questionnaires. Key findings indicated that while the informal sector contributes to income generation and enhances local livelihoods, challenges such as limited access to finance, governmental regulations and infrastructural inadequacies hinder its growth and sustainability. Correlation analysis indicates a strong positive relationship ($r = 0.63$) between business growth and loan access, underscoring the critical need for financial inclusion. Additionally, a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.52$) between business growth and income levels suggests that expanding enterprises enhance household earnings. Conversely, a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.72$) between unemployment and social vices highlights that rising joblessness contributes to increased crime rates. The researchers recommended improved financial inclusion, infrastructure development, and vocational training initiatives to enhance the informal sector's contribution to sustainable community development.

Keywords: Informal Sector, Community Development, Employment Generation, Skill Acquisition, Economic Empowerment

Introduction

The informal sector plays a significant role in the economy of developing countries, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa, including Nigeria (Onokerhoraye, 1977). It encompasses a wide range of economic activities that operate outside formal regulations, including petty trade, street vending, artisanship, transportation services, and small-scale manufacturing. According to the International Labour Organisation (ILO), the informal